

Supplementary Protocol S1

Review protocol and methodological transparency statement

Manuscript title:

Floating and Amphibious Architecture in Waterfront Built Environments: A Systematic Review of Climate Adaptation and Regenerative Potential

Manuscript ID: sustainability-4314880

Article type: Systematic Review

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Protocol version: Version 1.1

Date: 27 May 2026

Repository record: Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20411518

1. Protocol status and purpose

This document provides a retrospective review protocol and methodological transparency statement prepared during the revision of manuscript sustainability-4314880. The review was not prospectively registered before the search and screening process and does not constitute a preregistration. Its purpose is to document, in a consolidated and transparent form, the review aim, research questions, search strategy, eligibility criteria, study-selection process, data-extraction fields, coding framework, operationalisation of regenerative potential, quality-control procedures, evidence-appraisal strategy and synthesis approach used in the review.

The protocol was prepared to strengthen methodological transparency, facilitate assessment of the reproducibility of the review process and clarify the distinction between the screened publication landscape used for bibliometric profiling and the core evidence base used for qualitative synthesis.

2. Review aim and research questions

The aim of the review is to examine how floating and amphibious architecture is framed, assessed and operationalised within climate-responsive and regenerative waterfront built environments.

The review addresses three research questions:

RQ1. How does floating and amphibious architecture respond to climate-driven water-level variability, and what are the implications for the performance and function of the built environment?

RQ2. How are these typologies integrated, or not, into broader processes of urban development, regeneration and spatial governance along waterfronts?

RQ3. To what extent do they reflect a shift from conventional sustainability frameworks toward regenerative urbanism in practice?

These questions structure the qualitative synthesis and are linked to the coded variables used in the review. The cross-mapping between research questions, research gaps and analytical coding variables is provided in Table 2 of the manuscript.

3. Conceptual scope and definitions

For the purposes of this review, floating and amphibious architecture are treated as related but distinct water-adaptive typologies.

Floating architecture refers to buildings or structures designed to remain permanently buoyant and supported by floating platforms, pontoons, hull-based systems or other floating substructures. Floating systems are treated as permanently water-based adaptive typologies.

Amphibious architecture refers to buildings that normally rest on the ground or on fixed foundations but become buoyant and rise temporarily during inundation or flood events. Amphibious systems are treated as land-based but flood-activated adaptive typologies.

Other water-adapted typologies include waterfront, shoreline, ecological, hybrid or land-water interface systems retained where they had a clear architectural, urban-design or built-environment relevance.

Regenerative potential is not treated as an inherent property of floating or amphibious form. It is considered credible only where claims are supported by explicit ecological, socio-spatial, governance-related or performance-oriented evidence. Such evidence may include life-cycle assessment, post-occupancy evaluation, ecological monitoring, habitat enhancement, blue-green infrastructure or living-edge integration, off-grid or circular resource-flow systems, documented governance and stewardship mechanisms, or socio-spatial benefits such as accessibility, affordability, reduced displacement risk or continuity of use.

4. Information sources and search strategy

The review used two multidisciplinary bibliographic databases:

1. Web of Science Core Collection
2. Scopus

The search window for the systematic review and in-depth synthesis covered publications indexed between January 2015 and August 2025. Searches were last updated on 15 August 2025.

The search strategy combined terms related to water-adapted architectural typologies and waterfront built environments. The core search terms included variants of:

- floating architecture;
- amphibious architecture;
- waterfront architecture;
- shoreline architecture.

The database-specific search documentation reported 3,623 records from Web of Science and 5,230 records from Scopus, for a total of 8,853 records before deduplication.

Web of Science Core Collection

Date searched: 15 August 2025

Search field: Topic

Search string:

TS=("float* archit*" OR "amphib* archit*" OR "waterfront archit*" OR "shoreline archit*")

Scopus

Date searched: 15 August 2025

Search field: Title, Abstract, Keywords

Search string:

TITLE-ABS-KEY("float* archit*" OR "amphib* archit*" OR "waterfront archit*" OR "shoreline archit*")

Reference-list screening and forward citation tracking were used as sensitivity checks. These additional checks were intended to identify potentially relevant studies that might not have been captured through database-indexed retrieval.

5. Eligibility criteria and study selection

Studies were eligible for inclusion if they met all of the following criteria:

1. **Publication type:** peer-reviewed journal article, full-length peer-reviewed conference paper, proceedings paper or peer-reviewed book chapter.
2. **Time window:** published between January 2015 and August 2025.
3. **Language:** English-language publications were included. Non-English studies were included only where the full text was accessible and key data could be extracted reliably.
4. **Typology focus:** the study addressed floating, amphibious, hybrid or closely related water-adapted architectural typologies with an explicit architectural or urban-design dimension.
5. **Scale:** the study was relevant to buildings, public spaces, waterfronts, settlements, urban districts or broader urban/regional water-adaptive systems.
6. **Context and framing:** the study addressed at least one of the following: climate change, sea-level rise, water-level variability, climate adaptation, flood resilience, sustainability, regenerative design or waterfront redevelopment.
7. **Hydro-spatial relevance:** the study was located in, or directly relevant to, urban, peri-urban or settlement-scale waterfront contexts, including coastal, riverine, lake, estuarine, deltaic or harbour environments.

Studies were excluded if they were not peer-reviewed; focused on marine, offshore, naval or hydraulic engineering without architectural, urban-design or built-environment relevance; addressed climate change or flooding without reference to floating, amphibious or related water-adapted built typologies; focused on generic floating photovoltaic, offshore energy or marine infrastructure without built-environment relevance; fell outside the review period; or provided insufficient information for reliable extraction and coding.

The selection process followed PRISMA 2020 logic and consisted of record identification, export and integration, duplicate removal, title/abstract screening, detailed abstract-level relevance assessment, full-text retrieval, full-text eligibility assessment and final inclusion.

Searches identified 8,853 records before deduplication. After automatic and manual deduplication, 8,423 unique records remained. The screened publication landscape used for bibliometric profiling comprised N = 1,410 records, while N = 63 studies were retained as the core evidence base for qualitative synthesis.

Of the 8,423 records screened, 7,013 were excluded during title/abstract screening because they were clearly outside the review scope. The remaining 1,410 records constituted the screened publication landscape used for bibliometric profiling and detailed relevance assessment. Within this subset, 1,347 records were excluded during detailed abstract-level eligibility assessment because they did not meet the substantive inclusion criteria for the core evidence base. Sixty-three reports were then sought for retrieval, assessed for eligibility and retained as the core evidence base for qualitative synthesis.

The exclusion reasons per stage are reported in the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram presented as Figure 2 in the revised manuscript.

6. Data extraction and coding framework

A structured data-extraction template was used for the 63 included studies. The coding unit was a single study/publication. Coding was based on the full text of included studies wherever available. Where supplementary clarification was required, abstracts and metadata were used to support, but not replace, full-text interpretation.

Extracted metadata included:

- Study ID;
- year of publication;
- DOI;
- source type;
- full publication title;
- study context or location where available;
- research design;
- scale;
- function;
- confidence level;
- need for full-text verification.

Coding was conducted in two layers.

6.1 Layer 1: metadata and primary codes

Layer 1 captured the dominant characteristics of each study:

- **TYP_PRIMARY:** FLOAT, AMPH or OTHER;
- **FRAMING:** CCH, SUR or CCH+SUR;
- **HAZARD_PRIMARY:** FLOOD, WAVES_SURGE, HEAT, WQ_ECO, MULTI or SLR_SUBS;
- **SCALE_PRIMARY:** BUILD, WATERFRONT or CITY_REGION;
- **DESIGN_PRIMARY:** CASE, SIM_OPT or DESIGN_PROTO;

- **FUNCTION:** HOUSING or OTHER;
- **SETTING:** where available;
- **Confidence:** High, Medium or Low;
- **Needs_fulltext_check:** YES or NO.

Layer-1 coding was used to classify the typological focus, problem framing, dominant hazard, spatial scale, research design and primary function of the included studies.

Where a study addressed more than one typology, framing, hazard or scale, a single dominant code was assigned according to predefined dominance rules. The dominant typology was defined as the main analytical object of the study. The dominant framing was determined from the abstract, introduction and stated aim. The dominant hazard or driver was defined as the water-related or environmental pressure most directly analysed in the methods, results or central argument. The dominant scale was assigned according to the scale at which evidence was generated and interpreted. Secondary framings, typologies or hazards were recorded in qualitative notes where relevant but were not treated as separate primary codes.

6.2 Layer 2: binary implementation and co-benefit indicators

Layer 2 used binary 0/1 coding. A value of 1 was assigned only when a feature or topic was explicitly discussed as relevant in the study content, including aims, methods, results, discussion or recommendations. A value of 0 was assigned where the feature was absent, marginal, implicit or not sufficiently justified.

The binary indicators were:

1. **BUOYANT_FOUNDATION**
2. **RETROFIT_INPLACE**
3. **PUBLIC_REALM_INTEGRATION**
4. **NBS_LIVING_EDGES**
5. **OFFGRID_OPS**
6. **REGULATION_PERMITTING**
7. **FINANCE_VALUATION**
8. **O_M_STEWARDSHIP**
9. **UTILITIES_INTERFACES**
10. **EVIDENCE_LONGTERM**

These indicators were used to assess implementation-relevant dimensions, environmental and socio-spatial co-benefits, regulatory and operational constraints, and the availability of long-term evidence.

6.3 Study IDs and cross-referencing

Each included study was assigned a stable internal Study ID from S01 to S63. Study IDs are used consistently across Appendix A and Supplementary Tables S4–S7 to link the same publication across the complete coding matrix, evidence-strength appraisal, revision-stage coding harmonisation check and Study ID/reference crosswalk.

Study IDs do not correspond to the numbered reference list. Where table format allows, the corresponding manuscript reference number is reported in the Title [Ref.] field or in the Study ID/reference crosswalk. This cross-referencing procedure was introduced during revision to

improve traceability between internal coding identifiers, coding outputs and manuscript citations.

7. Operationalisation of regenerative potential

Regenerative potential was operationalised through explicit evidence rather than assumed from typological form or design intent.

A regenerative claim was treated as evidence-supported only if the study explicitly discussed one or more of the following:

1. ecological restoration or ecological enhancement;
2. habitat creation or habitat connectivity;
3. nature-based solutions, blue-green infrastructure or living-edge systems;
4. water-quality improvement or aquatic remediation;
5. circular material flows or resource-flow strategies;
6. off-grid or self-sufficient systems where treated as substantive performance issues;
7. life-cycle assessment, embodied-carbon assessment or circularity metrics;
8. post-occupancy evaluation, monitoring or long-term operational evidence;
9. documented governance, stewardship, maintenance or implementation mechanisms;
10. socio-spatial benefits, including access, affordability, reduced displacement risk, continuity of use or community resilience.

Regenerative aspirations that appeared only as broad conceptual or rhetorical claims were not coded as evidence-supported regenerative potential unless linked to explicit ecological, socio-spatial, governance-related or performance-oriented evidence.

8. Quality control, reliability and evidence-strength appraisal

Quality control was implemented through predefined eligibility criteria, structured extraction, two-layer coding, confidence flags, full-text verification flags and discussion-based resolution of uncertain or disputed cases.

Screening and full-text assessment were conducted by two reviewers, with disagreements resolved through discussion until consensus was reached. Coding decisions were checked against the predefined extraction template and codebook.

No formal inter-rater agreement statistic was calculated during the initial screening and coding process. However, coding definitions were clarified during the early extraction phase, and all final records were rechecked during the revision-stage harmonisation procedure.

Because the evidence base is heterogeneous and includes case studies, modelling/simulation studies, design-research contributions, conceptual studies and review-oriented work, a conventional risk-of-bias tool designed for clinical or quantitative intervention studies was not directly applicable. A structured quality-appraisal procedure was therefore introduced to qualify the strength and transparency of evidence rather than to exclude studies retrospectively.

Each included study was assessed using the following criteria:

1. **Methodological transparency:** clarity of aim, data sources, methods and analytical procedure.

2. **Evidence specificity and triangulation:** degree to which claims are supported by specific case evidence, modelling, empirical data, monitoring, design documentation, multiple data sources or clearly reported analytical material.
3. **Contextual transferability:** clarity of geographical, hydrological, spatial and governance context.
4. **Implementation relevance:** reporting of regulation, permitting, utilities, maintenance, finance, governance, stewardship or operational constraints.
5. **Environmental and performance validation:** presence of LCA, ecological monitoring, post-occupancy evaluation, durability evidence, energy/IEQ analysis or other performance validation.
6. **Reflexivity and limitations:** acknowledgement of uncertainty, contextual limits, methodological constraints or risks of overgeneralisation.

Each criterion was scored as:

- 0 – absent or unclear;
- 1 – partially addressed;
- 2 – clearly addressed.

Total appraisal categories were defined as:

- **High evidentiary support:** 9–12;
- **Moderate evidentiary support:** 5–8;
- **Limited evidentiary support:** 0–4.

The appraisal was used to qualify the strength of evidence and support cautious interpretation. It did not alter the composition of the core evidence base unless a serious eligibility inconsistency was identified. The appraisal results for all 63 included studies are reported in Supplementary Table S5.

A revision-stage coding harmonisation check was conducted to improve internal consistency of the coding process. The check focused on the five main analytical codes: typology, framing, hazard, scale and research design. All coding decisions were rechecked against the final codebook and predefined dominance rules; discrepancies were resolved through discussion and used to clarify coding definitions where necessary. This procedure documents internal harmonisation of the final coding matrix and is not equivalent to formal inter-rater reliability assessment based on prospective independent parallel coding. Because formal agreement coefficients were not calculated during the initial screening and coding process, Cohen's κ is not reported. The absence of a formal agreement statistic is acknowledged as a methodological limitation in Section 2.8 of the manuscript. The results of this harmonisation check are reported in Supplementary Table S6.

9. Synthesis strategy

The synthesis was qualitative and interpretive rather than meta-analytic. Quantitative meta-analysis was not conducted because the included studies varied substantially in research design, scale, evidence type, outcome indicators and evaluation frameworks.

The synthesis involved:

1. descriptive aggregation of coded study characteristics;
2. bibliometric mapping of the screened publication landscape;
3. keyword co-occurrence and thematic mapping using VOSviewer;

4. comparison across typology, framing, hazard, scale and research design;
5. qualitative thematic synthesis of technological, socio-spatial, ecological, governance and implementation patterns;
6. interpretation of regenerative claims in relation to evidence support;
7. identification of research gaps and future research priorities.

The screened publication landscape was used for bibliometric profiling, while qualitative claims were based on the core evidence base of 63 included studies.

Bibliometric mapping settings

VOSviewer was used for keyword co-occurrence mapping. The unit of analysis was author keywords and database-indexed terms. A full counting method was applied. The minimum occurrence threshold was set at 2 occurrences to retain interpretable keyword clusters while limiting isolated single-occurrence terms. Before mapping, keywords were harmonised by merging synonyms, correcting spelling variants and removing generic terms.

10. Limitations and transparency statement

The protocol acknowledges the following methodological limitations:

1. The review was not prospectively registered before the search and screening process.
2. This protocol was prepared retrospectively during revision as a methodological transparency document.
3. The core corpus was restricted to peer-reviewed publications indexed in Scopus and Web of Science.
4. Grey literature, professional reports, government guidelines, theses, design competition entries and industry documents were excluded from the PRISMA core corpus.
5. This exclusion supports bibliographic reproducibility but may underrepresent vernacular, regional, practice-based and policy-oriented knowledge. In regions where floating and amphibious implementation knowledge circulates primarily through government guidance, technical standards or practice reports, particularly in the Netherlands, Japan, Vietnam, Thailand and Southeast Asia more broadly, the review may underestimate the current state of applied practice.
6. Some relevant non-English or locally embedded studies may be underrepresented.
7. The evidence base is heterogeneous, limiting the possibility of meta-analysis.
8. Regenerative potential was assessed through reported evidence, not independently verified environmental or social performance.
9. The review identifies evidence patterns, implementation conditions and knowledge gaps rather than causal effectiveness of floating or amphibious architecture.

Practice-oriented sources, including government guidance, technical standards, professional reports and industry documents, were not incorporated into the PRISMA core corpus because they were not searched and screened through the same reproducible bibliographic procedure. Where relevant, selected practice-oriented sources may be discussed in the revised manuscript as contextual implementation evidence, clearly distinguished from the systematically selected peer-reviewed core evidence base.

11. Data availability and supplementary materials

Supplementary Table S1 provides the completed PRISMA 2020 checklist. Supplementary Table S2 provides the database-specific search strings. Supplementary Table S3 provides the

codebook. Supplementary Table S4 provides the complete coding matrix for all included studies (N = 63). Supplementary Table S5 provides the evidence-strength appraisal matrix for the core evidence base (N = 63). Supplementary Table S6 provides the revision-stage coding harmonisation check for the final analytical coding scheme. Supplementary Table S7 provides the Study ID/reference crosswalk for the core evidence base (N = 63).

Protocol S1 provides a retrospective review protocol and methodological transparency statement. Supplementary Figure S1 provides the stage-specific study-selection and exclusion workflow. Supplementary Figures S2–S5 provide additional bibliometric, geographical and contextual visualisations supporting the interpretation of the screened publication landscape and the included evidence base.

The PRISMA 2020 flow diagram is presented as Figure 2 in the revised manuscript. This protocol complements the manuscript, Appendix A and Supplementary Materials by consolidating the review design, coding logic, operational definitions, evidence-appraisal approach, synthesis strategy and transparency statement in a single document.